

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

EDGE IMPACT AND COMPRESSION AFTER EDGE IMPACT SIMULATIONS IN CFRP LAMINATES

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Introduction

- The performance of composite structural parts, particularly for application in aero-structures, is usually assessed by means of a “building-block” approach consisting of a combination of testing and analysis.
- While the testing alone is prohibitively expensive and time consuming, analysis currently needs additional validation to ensure that it can correctly represent the structural response of composites under complex loading conditions.
- In this work, a modification of a composite damage model is used to predict damage formation and structural failure at higher levels of the test pyramid. Here, edge impact and compression after edge impact (CAEI) scenarios are analyzed, which mimic, at the coupon scale, an impact to the top edge of a stringer.

Composite damage meso-model

- Composite intralaminar damage is characterized by **different fracture modes**.
- For the complete definition of the constitutive model it is necessary to define appropriate **damage activation functions**, i.e. the conditions that lead to the onset of inelastic response.
- Having defined the damage activation criteria, **damage evolution functions**, which will govern damage propagation, are then required to model the softening behaviour and bridging phenomena observed on polymer composites.

Composite damage meso-model

Ply modelling

- **Continuum damage mechanics** model.
- Simulation of **progressive intralaminar damage** mechanisms (matrix cracking and fibre breakage).
- Applicable for **unidirectional** composite tapes (ply-by-ply modelling of multidirectional laminates).
- **Material properties** obtained from **ply-based test methods**.
- The ***in situ* effect** is accounted for based on analytical solutions.
- Automatic **strength reduction** (allowing the use of larger elements).

Interface modelling

- **Abaqus built-in** cohesive interface interactions
- **Linear constitutive law**
- **Mixed-mode propagation** (BK energy criterion)

Improved composite meso-model

- Classic composite damage models assume that the out-of-plane stress components are negligibly small to promote damage, and therefore only the in-plane stress components of the stress tensor activate damage.
- However, this assumption is not suitable for test cases where the triaxiality of the stress state is not negligible.
- To improve the ability to accurately predict damage initiation and evolution in 3D test cases, composite damage models can be modified to include a 3D invariant-based failure criterion for fibre kinking.

Improved composite meso-model

- This failure criterion is used to define an **effective in-plane shear strength**, which represents the effect of hydrostatic pressure on the shear response of the polymer matrix.

Improved composite meso-model

- The 3D invariant-based failure criterion for fibre kinking included in the damage model is also used to scale the **fracture toughness for longitudinal compression** and the **longitudinal compressive strength ratio at the inflection point** as a function of the applied pressure.

$$f_{XC}^{ef} = \min \{1, f_{XC} (1 - f_{fxc} \langle -I_3 \rangle)\}$$

$$I_3 = \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}$$

Improved composite meso-model

- Experimental evidence also shows that the mode II fracture toughness virtually increases when the cracking faces are compressed against each other. At the ply level, this means that transverse compressive stresses should affect the fracture toughness associated with in-plane shear fracture. Therefore, an **effective fracture toughness for in-plane shear** is proposed.

$$G_6^{ef} = G_6 (1 - \eta_G \langle -\sigma_{22} \rangle)$$

Virtual testing

Compression after edge impact test case

T700/M21 carbon-epoxy unidirectional prepreg

Stacking sequence (24 plies)

$[90/45/0_3/-45/0_2/45/90/-45/0]_s$

B. Ostré et al. / Composite Structures 152 (2016) 767–778

Virtual testing

Compression after edge impact test case

T700/M21 carbon-epoxy unidirectional prepreg

Stacking sequence (24 plies)

$[90_2/-45_2/0_4/45_2/0_2]_s$

Ostré et al. J Compos Mater 2015;49(13):1599-1612

B. Ostré et al. / Composite Structures 152 (2016) 767–778

Virtual testing

Compression after edge impact test case

T700/M21 carbon-epoxy unidirectional prepreg

Stacking sequence (24 plies)

[45₂/0₂/-45₂/0₄/90₂]S

B. Ostré et al. / Composite Structures 152 (2016) 767-778

Concluding remarks

- The proposed modelling strategy based on an advanced composite damage model that accounts for intralaminar damage mechanisms, and on cohesive surface interactions that account for interlaminar damage can predict with reasonable accuracy not only the shape and size of the damage inflicted by edge impact events, but also the residual strength of composite laminates subjected to CAEI tests.
- More importantly, the model can accurately capture stacking sequence effects; in agreement with experimental observations, significant changes in the mechanical response were well predicted by the proposed model when only the stacking sequence changes.
- The ability of the proposed model to accurately capture the edge impact and compression after impact response of different composite laminates opens new perspectives for its use on material qualification through virtual testing at high levels of the test pyramid, and to assess the effect of parameters associated with this type of events (such as eccentricity of the impact location, impact angle or geometry of the impactor) without resorting to complex, costly and time-consuming experimental testing